

Target interval	Indicative depth range (km) (focussed on continental domains unless otherwise specified)	Main geological and geophysical technique(s)	Comment	References
Lower mantle	~660 - 2890 km	Seismic tomography; Gravity/geoid	Structures include subducted slabs, mantle plumes, core boundary dynamics. Seismic data typically developed from global models. Limited resolution, coverage and sensitivity.	Jakovlev et al. (2012), Rickers et al. (2013), Panet et al. (2014), Gaina et al. (2014), Toyokuni et al. (2020a, b), Celli et al. (2021)
Upper mantle (including mantle transition zone)	~100-660 km Lithosphere-asthenosphere boundary (LAB) to base of the transition zone	Receiver functions of converted seismic waves, seismic tomography, gravity/geoid	Structures include subducting slabs, mantle plumes, mineral phase change in transition zones. Data limitations as for lower mantle.	Schaeffer and Lebedev (2013), Wilde-Piörko (2015)
Lithosphere-asthenosphere boundary (LAB)	~60-280 km under continents ~30-120 km under oceans	seismic, electromagnetic, petrological, thermal and gravity data	Major lateral variation from thin (12km) lithosphere at the mid-ocean ridge to 90-100 km beneath the Barents Sea	Klitzke et al. (2015), Minakov (2018), Grad and Majorowicz (2020)
Deeper parts of the crust and uppermost mantle	~20-100 km	wide-angle reflection/refraction seismic and seismological methods; Magnetotelluric data; Volcanic rocks (i.e. xenoliths)	Provides insights into electrical conductivity (i.e. fluid content)	Amundsen et al. (1987), Skjelkvåle et al. (1989), Ionov et al. (2002a, b), Griffin et al. (2012), Wilde-Piörko (2015), Goncharov et al. (2015), Czuba (2017), Selway et al. (2020), Senger et al. (2024)
Deep to shallow crust	~0-40 km	Magnetotelluric data; Seismic reflection data; Gravity and magnetic data (potential field). GNSS stations;	Used for geothermal exploration near Longyearbyen and Ny Ålesund; Provides insights onto the subsurface structures, and outcrop-seismic correlations. Burial and exhumation history of various rocks; Calculate exposure ages and erosion rates	Eiken (1985, 1994), Faleide et al. (1988), Olesen et al. (2010), Bælum et al. (2012), Dörr et al. (2012), Senger et al. (2013); Blinova et al. (2013); Gjermundsen et al. (2015), Beka et al. (2015, 2016, 2017) Dumais and Brönnner (2020)
Surface and uppermost crust (including sediments)	~0-10 km	GNSS stations; Apatite fission track; Cosmogenic nucleides/exposure dating Heat flow and thermal conductivity; outcropping geology	Quaternary geology and surface outcrops. Recent and ongoing uplift, mostly located in western Svalbard. Onshore and offshore data. Heat flow measured offshore Svalbard increases from 80mW/m ² near the continental slope to >300 mW/m ² along the mid-ocean spreading zones	Crane et al. (1991), Okay and Crane (1993), Geissler et al. (2014), Dumke et al. (2016), Klitzke et al. (2016), Grad and Majorowicz (2020), Kierulf et al. (2022b, a) Senger et al. 2023b)

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